

Innovative concepts and technologies for ECologically sustainable NUTRient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

Newsletter – Issue 1

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WELCOME

Welcome to the first edition of the **Econutri** Newsletter! Within these pages, you will find news and updates on our activities. We invite you to subscribe and explore our website! Follow us on social media and learn more about the world of **Econutri** and its accomplishments.

[Econutri website](#)

What is Econutri about?

The **Econutri** project, an Innovation Action (IA) under Horizon Europe, is dedicated to researching novel technologies aimed at optimizing nutrient management, particularly concerning nitrogen and phosphorus. These nutrients, when improperly managed, pose environmental threats by leaching into soil and water or evaporating into the atmosphere. **Econutri** aims to deploy nature-based solutions to mitigate these challenges, simultaneously targeting a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions associated with agricultural activities, contributing to overall sustainability within the farming sector.

Econutri follows a **holistic approach**, meaning that it considers soil, water and air as different components of the same organism, namely the ecosystem, and aims to address not only impacts of single polluting sources but also their interactions and interconnections. The holistic approach considers a complex system, (here, the nutrient cycle in agriculture), as a coherent whole that is also part of something greater. Thus, ultimately, the core of **Econutri** is the development of a circular agricultural production

Project Framework

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Innovation program under the Grant Agreement No. 101081858.

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system, in which organic waste biomass is processed to recover plant nutrients and returned to the soil to support a sustainable production with minimal polluting emissions, towards a zero-pollution target.

Overview of the Consortium

Econutri is coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens, located in Greece and it consists of 30 partners, 24 originate from Europe and 6 from China.

Econutri brings together a robust and complementary range of expertise spanning research, producer organizations, scientific disciplines such as agronomy, soil science, microbiology, plant physiology, engineering, socio-economics, life cycle assessment (LCA), and land use modeling. This diverse knowledge base offers detailed insights into both environmental impacts and ecosystem functions. Additionally, the consortium includes a diverse team of experts from China, fostering a fully inclusive, multi-actor, and transdisciplinary culture within **Econutri**.

This collaboration will lead to enhanced scientific and technological ties among Europe and China facilitating international implementation of the project's outcomes.

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What are the main goals of Econutri?

The main goals of **Econutri** are to:

- Reduce within safe ecological boundaries the nutrient losses from manure/slurry and plant residues.
- Optimize fertilizer use and maximize nutrient use efficiency (NUE) in conventional and organic open field and greenhouse crops to minimize pollution of ground and surface water resources by leaching of nutrients.
- Contribute to reduction of GHG emissions from agriculture in EU and China without impairing the potential of the plant and animal production.
- Scale up the adoption of the novel technologies optimized and validated during the project and increase awareness across the agri-food sector and the society about the farm to fork strategy of EU towards zero pollution.

The overall concept of Econutri is to optimize and validate at operational environment innovative technologies that halt nitrogen and phosphorus pollution and limit N/P emission but are still at the lab level and scale up their adoption in the agricultural sector, thus providing a decisive push to their transfer from the lab to the industry and the field.

Where are the demonstration sites?

Eight demonstration sites have been carefully selected to validate and demonstrate 24 innovative technologies selected by **Econutri**. These demonstration sites represent various groups of innovative technologies (biowaste treatment, crop fertilization, air pollution) and at the same time cover a wide range of climatic, social and cultural conditions, as well as specific agricultural systems in Europe and China.

The aim of the demonstration sites is to:

- a) test, validate and make accessible the **Econutri** core concepts and solutions,
- b) to establish a vibrant local open innovation community, where co-creation processes, platforms for innovation, people awareness-to-engagement, and acceleration towards local transition take place and
- c) to provide all relevant stakeholders, and especially local SMEs and professionals, with evidence of performance and usability of the

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developed concepts and solutions with appropriate business models.

The demonstration sites and the partners involved are the following:

1. UK/Edinburgh – JHI
2. Belgium – EL ILVO
3. Petrousa Drama, Greece – WP & AUA
4. Fields spread over Germany, Netherlands, Belgium, Italy – VERVAET
5. Skierniewice, PL – INHORT
6. Brandenburg, Germany – ATB
7. Beijing, China – CAU & Qinggang County, China – HAAS
8. Shandong-East China- SVG

Highlights during the first year of the project

1. The **Econutri** kick-off meeting was held in Athens, Greece on 30 November to 2 December 2022. All partners got together to celebrate the start of **Econutri**. Participants engaged in extensive discussions, setting the stage for the successful implementation of the project.

A standout moment was the enlightening field trip on the third day. Attendees visited the greenhouse facilities of key stakeholder, IGC (Intelligent Green Crops) S.A., gaining valuable insights into advanced agricultural technologies. The excursion concluded with a visit to the renowned archaeological site of Delphi, adding cultural and historical significance to the experience. More information [here](#).

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2. Our partners [Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops](#) (IGZ) and [Università degli Studi di Torino](#) (UNITO), held a highly productive partnership meeting on 13 July, 2023. UNITO updated on WP2 progress, focusing on innovative technologies to reduce nutrient pollution, while IGZ addressed environmental and socioeconomic considerations. More information [here](#).

3. Our coordinator and colleagues from [Agricultural University of Athens](#) (AUA) participated in the "[9th South-Eastern Europe Symposium on Vegetables and Potatoes](#)", which took place in Bucharest from 5–9 September, 2023. More information [here](#).

4. Our partners in the [James Hutton Institute](#), Umut Kartal and Pete Iannetta, had the opportunity to showcase their research at the [4th International Legume Society Meeting](#) in Granada from 19–22 September 2023. Their presentation at the event centered on legume-based crop systems, focusing on ecological intensification, as part of the Econutri project. For more information go [here](#).

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5. Our expert teams at [Leibniz Institute for Agricultural Engineering and Bioeconomy](#) (ATB) and [Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research Technology](#) (EV ILVO) came together in a workshop conducted 12-13 October, 2023, where they shared invaluable experiences on emission measurement and standardization protocols.

6. Econutri has made its journey across the Atlantic with a collaborative work from our partners [Leibniz Institute of Vegetable and Ornamental Crops](#) (IGZ) and [University of Thessaly](#) (UTH), at [GreenSys2023](#): International Symposium on New Technologies for Sustainable Greenhouse Systems in Cancun, Mexico. The conference took place on 22-27 October 2023. The presentation title was 'Evapotranspiration prediction for suitable combinations of cascade hydroponic systems. To learn more visit [here](#).

7. A Stakeholder Group (SHG) is currently in formation, involving stakeholders from academia, industries, and farming. This dynamic process entails continuous interaction between partners and stakeholders throughout the project, focusing on planning and implementation to maximize results, uptake, and impact. Stakeholders are encouraged to formally register their intention to engage with the project on the project [website](#).

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Future Events

1. Ecomodo – Italian exhibition November 2023
2. General Assembly meeting November 22 2024
3. Chinese kickoff meeting at Beijing, China November 16 2023
4. 3rd International Workshop on Vertical Farming ([VertiFarm2024](#))

Econutri Partners

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